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Abstract

This document describes the deployment scenarios in three locations according to the project description. The document gives an overview of the physical installation scenarios and its status as it is by April 1st 2025.

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Executive Summary

The installation of sensing devices discussed in this document is like installation of any other network equipment in a server or communication room but with some additional concern regarding acoustic noise and vibrational acceleration noise which should be at a minimum level as possible.

Choose of optical fibre is important but not essential. The recommendation is using silica core fibre with low loss as it is used for general telecommunication purposes.

The main challenge is to identify security issues regarding the data management and identify the national shareholder/s who has authority and expertise to analyse and interpret the data from DAS specific and also generally from all type of sensing devices.

Coordination between the shareholders and agree upon a clear interface and responsibilities between them is key issue to success.

1 Introduction

The SUBMERSE project aims to develop a multinational, multi stakeholder, research instrument, which can generate and sharing data about the earth from existing, in use submarine telecommunications cables. Such an instrument has not been developed before. This poses significant challenges to how such a system could be set up. It is also an opportunity to act as a pathfinder project to develop technologies which could benefit multiple research communities. In the project proposal there had been identified three possible geographical location to build such a sensing environment. This document describes the deployment scenarios in these three locations which later have been extended some other locations. The document gives an overview of the physical installation scenarios and its status as it is by April 1st 2025.

2 Instrument deployments

2.1 Project proposal deployment

The Table 1 describes the indicative site locations and details about experiment intentions as proposed by the Horizon Europe – RIA SUBMERSE Proposal Part B 20220420

Site Name	Cable A end	Cable B end	Cable type	Experiments	Scientific Interest
Svalbard , Norway	Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard	Longyearbyen, Svalbard	2 semi-parallel 256 km cable legs, repeaterless	DAS, SOP, bidirectional SOP with high precision timing, SOP OTDR	Gulf stream, seismology, volcanology, cetology, Atlantic atmospheric ocean interaction, gas leakage, ship traffic, noise from glaciers
Rhodes, Greece	Rhodes, Greece	Samos, Greece	200 km cable, terrestrial repeaters	DAS, SOP, SOP OTDR	Volcanology, Seismology, Mediterranean Sea atmospheric interaction, ship traffic.
Sines, Portugal	Sines, Portugal	Fortaleza, Brazil	5962 km cable, deep sea submarine repeaters	DAS, SOP, SOP OTDR	Mid-Atlantic ridge, sea bottom observations, seismology, volcanology, cetology, Atlantic atmospheric ocean interaction, ship traffic.
Fortaleza, Brazil	Fortaleza, Brazil	Sines, Portugal	5962 km cable, deep sea submarine repeaters	SOP, SOP OTDR	Mid-Atlantic ridge, sea bottom observations, seismology, volcanology, cetology, Atlantic atmospheric ocean interaction.
Madeira , Portugal	Funchal, Madeira*	Sines, Portugal	1116 km (GeoLab 56 km) cable, deep sea submarine repeaters	DAS (on GeoLab cable)	Mid-Atlantic ridge, sea bottom observations, seismology, volcanology, cetology, Atlantic atmospheric ocean interaction, ship traffic.

Table 1 Proposed site location in the project proposal

2.2 Ideal deployment scenario as we see it today

The necessary infrastructure and equipment needed to create a good sensing environment on existing telecom fibre infrastructure are as follow.

2.2.1 Cable and Fibre

Single mode and solid core fibre with low loss are preferable fibre types. Coupling of the fibre to the subsurface has been shown to greatly affect the data quality of DAS data. In the Svalbard dataset, where most of the data is from a submarine environment, we see a clear difference between buried and unburied fibre sections. The portion of fibre buried in 0 to 2 m of sediments shows a significantly higher signal quality than the fibre portion located directly on bedrock. The burial depth is not crucial. This is because the wavelength of what is to be detected is long in relation to how quickly the wave field decreases downwards in the sediments and the typical burial depth of such cables, i.e. 0-3 meters. We have not seen particularly large variations in the type of seabed for buried cables.

In other terrestrial applications the same pattern is observed. There are many sources of waves that propagate on land. Thus, a fibre will be stretch modulated by many more signals than those you are typically looking to measure. The picture here is therefore much more complex! On land, you can get strong DAS signals with fibre cable laid in a cable duct and directly buried in the ground.

In aerial cable is often the oscillations in the poles that contribute to the strongest signals. This means it is easy to detect signals from waves in the land that cause the poles to oscillate. There can be many sources for this. In addition to wind that directly causes oscillation of the poles.

The ideal fibre deployment scenario is the environment with lowest possible noise where the cable is buried or properly in touch with the ground surface.

2.2.2 Site condition

The sensing unit installation site should have low acoustic noise and low vibrational acceleration level. Typical sources for such a noise are accelerating fan.

2.2.3 Sensing instruments

In our trials we have been using devices which can detect the state of polarization and its changes and Rayleigh scattering-based distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) devices.

2.2.4 Stakeholders

The number of stake holders and a good relationship between them is very important in the process. High number of stakeholders and scattered ownership to the different part of the sensing infrastructure will add complexity to the sensing process.

Project owner, Equipment owner, cable owner, fibre owner, site owner, data connectivity provider, storage and computational facility, long term storage owner, authority and relationship to the security agencies are some of the typical stake holders. From day one, the project should create a common understanding of sensing process between stakeholders and make sure that there is a clear interface and demarcation point between stake holder's contribution and responsibilities.

3 Country deployments

3.1 Norway – Where are we at this stage compared with the initial proposal

3.1.1 Svalbard Fibre Connectivity

Two repeaterless submarine fibre optic (G652.D) cables run Between Longyearbyen and Ny-Ålesund. The length of each cable is approximately 250 km, and each cable holds multiple optical fibres. In Figure 1 the cables are shown with the blue area identifying where the fibre is untrenched and is located at shallow depth (< 100m). Between this area and Ny-Ålesund, the cable is located much deeper (> ~250m), making it unusually quiet. Currently we are running both DAS units and all four polarimeters on route 2 (see the picture below).

Figure 1 Fibre optic cables between Longyearbyen to ny-Ålesund

3.1.2 Svalbard overall setup diagram and equipment.

The Figure 2 shows an overview of the installed DAS and SOP units with underlying DWDM and fibre/cable infrastructure. As of today, we there are 4 polarimeters units and 2 DAS units installed in Svalbard. The ASN DAS unit is owned by NTNU and have been installed in 2023. DAS unit from Alcalá university (UAH) is owned by UAH and targeting to monitor seabed temperature.

The equipment configuration in Svalbard is depicted in Figure 2. Also, the stakeholders of this site are the following:

1. Sikt
 - a. Cable owner
 - b. Connectivity to sensing units
 - c. Storage (short and long-term for polarimeters)
 - d. The University Centre in Svalbard AS (UNIS), landing station and housing facilities in Longyearbyen. Sikt has dedicated space for equipment.
 - e. KingsBay, landing station and housing facilities in Ny-Ålesund. Sikt has dedicated space for equipment.
2. NTNU
 - a. ASN DAS and Novoptel SOP owner
 - b. DAS pre-processing and Raw buffer facilitator
3. ASN – OptoDAS and technical support
4. University of Alcalá - Alcalá DAS
5. Cesnet– Polbox provider and support
6. Sigma2: National Storage facilitator

Since Sikt is the fibre/cable owner and in addition provides space, network connectivity and storage facilities make the progress much smoother and faster than a scenario based on scattered stakeholders' responsibilities and role.

Figure 2 Svalbard overall setup diagram and equipment.

3.1.3 Data processing and availability phase

The Figure 3 shows the data management as it is handled in Norway. A local short-term storage is connected to the DAS-units. The short-term storage is connected to the Sikt's IP-network through a 1GbE connection. The data from the local storage will be downloaded to the "storage and analyse" site at NTNU in Trondheim. In this stage only few authorized personal from NTNU have access to the data.

Sikt is responsible to download the data from all four polarimeters to Sikt's storage unit in Trondheim. The SOP units from Novoptel haven't any local storage connected to the units. The data from these units is streamed in real-time to the Sikt's storage in Trondheim. The polarimeters units from Cesnet (Polbox) are equipped by local disk and the data from these units are getting downloaded regularly at least once a week.

After DAS pre-processing phase the required data from all polarimeters and DAS units will get available to project partners via the storage facilities at Sigma2 in Lefdal datacentre.

The common practise is that we release only the SOP data from the same period as DAS data have been released.

Figure 3 Data flow from sensing device to the user accessibility

3.1.4 Timing distribution

1. Thought the fibre network with white rabbit protocol

The Norwegian mapping authority, Kartverket, owns a hydrogen maser atomic clock in the Ny-Ålesund. Sikt is using this as a clock source for their Svalbard network. In the Kartverket site, Sikt has one White Rabbit Switch (WRS) installed and configured as a grand master, receiving 1pps and 10MHz signals and distributing the time to Sikt's Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen sites where the sensing equipment is installed, as illustrated in Figure 2. The grandmaster WRS is connected to the boundary clock WRS in Sikt's site in Ny-Ålesund through a bidirectional 1390/1410 channel in a single dedicated fibre circa 5km. Towards Longyearbyen, this WRS is using a DWDM channel to Longyearbyen together with production traffic. Because the connection is using a fibre pair, asymmetry is introduced because different fibre lengths that can vary up to hundreds of meters, where one meter introduces circa 4.9 nanoseconds of time error. Hence, during the project work, the asymmetry introduced by the fibre pair was measured as to be compensated in the white rabbit node.

Since all sensing equipment have coaxial ports for timing, 1pps input, and the WR switches in use have only one coaxial port for 1pps, Signal Distribution Units (SDU) are installed both in Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen to distribute the time to multiple sensing units, as illustrated in Figure 2.

- Ny-Ålesund:
 - o SOP unit from Novoptel
 - o SOP unit from Cesnet

- Longyearbyen
 - o SOP unit from Novoptel
 - o SOP unit from Cesnet

At this stage, the Alacala Phi-OTDR DAS prototype is using GPS (without the antenna connected) for the internal clock of the system (the clock that synchronizes all the signals) and the PC's clock for the timestamp of the data that is saved to the hard disk.

2. Through Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)

The C-band OptoDAS is as January 2025 installed in a second Sikt site room in Ny-Ålesund where there is not WRS node installed. In this site the timing information is received through a GPS unit and given to the OptoDAS through 1pps signal to its coaxial input port.

During the L-band optoDAS tests in Q4 2023, and for comparison with C-band optoDAS, both units were connected to the same GPS unit: the C-band optoDAS was the primary node receiving the signal and was further connected to the L-band optoDAS with coaxial port and giving it the time through 1pps signal.

3.1.5 Instruments deployment and roadmap

The Table 2 describes the indicative site locations and details about experiment intentions described in SUBMERSE Proposal PART B.

Site Name	Cable A end	Cable B end	Cable type	Experiments	Scientific Interest
Svalbard, Norway	Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard	Longyearbyen, Svalbard	2 semi-parallel 256 km cable legs, repeaterless	DAS, SOP, bidirectional SOP with high precision timing, SOP OTDR	Gulf stream, seismology, volcanology, cetology, Atlantic atmospheric ocean interaction, gas leakage, ship traffic, noise from glaciers

Table 2 Initial plan for deployment in Svalbard

Table 3 describes the status of Svalbard deployment as of 01.02.2025 compared to the proposal deployment, and roadmap.

Site Name	Cable type and System	Sensing technology	Experiments Performed as of 01.03.2025
Ny-Ålesund	Route 2 - DWDM system	OptoDAS L-band	Performed Q3.2023 After the experiments L-band DAS removed Q2.2024 Experiments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L-band DAS vs C-band DAS
		Novoptel SOP	In place from Q3.2023
		Polbox SOP	In place from Q1.2024
		SOP OTDR* (Nokia Bell labs coherent)	Planned – Q3.2025

	Route 2 - Dark Fibre	OptoDas C-band	Installed Q3.2023 - running Experiments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inner cable vs. outer cable (2xDAS) - C-band vs L-band test
		Alcala Chirped-Pulse-phi-OTDR DAS	Installed Q3.2024 - running
Longyearbyen	Route 2	Novoptel SOP(2 units)	In place from Q1.2024 - running
	DWDM system	Polbox SOP (2 units)	In place from Q3.2024 - running

Table 3 : Deployment log in Svalbard from project start to March 2025

As shown in the tables all installations planned in SUBMERSE Proposal PART B have been finalized and data gathering is on-going, i.e. instruments are running. Great

3.1.6 Evaluation of L-band DAS on Telecom Link with Live Traffic

In 2023 we did preform lab-based and field-based test to prove that it is possible to combine DAS sensing and DWDM-based fibre optic installation in the same fibre. The field experiment comparing the signal response of DAS when operating in a dedicated dark fibre and when operating in coexistence with a live dense division wavelength multiplexing (DWDM) telecommunications system. We demonstrate the performance of the DWDM wavelengths under coexistence with the DAS probe signal and analyse the comparative sensing response to a range of environmental phenomena for a C-band DAS unit connected to a dedicated dark fibre and a L-band DAS unit connected to a fibre carrying live DWDM telecom data traffic in the C-band, both fibres located within the same submarine telecom cable. The experiment was conducted in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard, as part of the SUBMERSE project 1 and Center for Geophysical Forecasting at NTNU (CGF) research centres 2.

We have demonstrated uncompromised L-band DAS and telecom coexistence in a live telecom link carrying production traffic with DWDM signals, with no noticeable increase in Pre-FEC BER, Post-FEC BER and Q-factor. We compared the performance between C-band DAS interrogating a dark fibre in the same submarine cable as the L-Band DAS multiplexed onto a live telecom fibre and found that the L-band DAS under coexistence with traffic provides the same range and sensitivity as the C-band DAS on the dedicated dark fibre. Even though the L-band was connected to the submarine cable through a 10 dB of additional insertion loss, all the events observed were adequately perceivable on both the C-band DAS and L-band DAS. Our analyses demonstrates that both DAS units were equally sensitive to a catalogued seismic event and showing equal event amplitude.

We are preparing a journal paper based on these activities and will be soon submit to JOURNAL OF LIGHTWAVE TECHNOLOGY

3.2 Portugal – Where are we at this stage compared with the ideal

The initial proposal outlined the deployment of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology at two key locations in Portugal: Sines, on the mainland, and Madeira, an offshore island. Several technical challenges have been encountered, and significant efforts have been made by stakeholders to overcome them. Currently, two DAS units are installed, but only the one in Madeira is streaming data. For State of Polarization (SOP) monitoring, the installation of a polarimeter in Sines has been delayed as we continue to assess the configuration of the submarine cable's data transmission system and determine the best approach for implementation. The following sections present the results obtained to date.

3.2.1 Sines overall setup diagram and equipment

Figure 4 : Sines overall setup diagram and equipment

The equipment configuration in Sines is depicted In Figure 4. Also, the stakeholders of this site are the following:

1. EllaLink (Sines, Portugal) – Cable landing station (CLS)
2. FCCN – Connectivity
3. INESC TEC – Storage (short-term)
4. ASN – OptoDAS and technical support
5. GEANT – Rack and fibre pair (FP2)

3.2.1.1. Instrument deployment

The submarine fibre optic cable starts at EllaLink’s Cable landing station (CLS) and links Sines, in Portugal to Fortaleza, in Brazil. The cable is 5962 km long and Figure 5 shows a representative location of the submarine cable.

A C-band OptoDAS system, provided by ASN, was installed in GEANT’s rack and connected to the available Fibre Pair 2 (FP2 - dark fibre, G.652). An FC/APC – LC/UPC single mode fibre patch-cord is required to connect the interrogator to the fibre under study (FC/APC - Ferrule Connector/Angled Physical Connect, LC/UPC - Lucent Connector/Ultra Physical Contact). Additionally, two power inverters were installed (one for redundancy), each with a capacity of 1.2 kW, enabling the conversion to -54VDC voltage. FCCN provided a 10Gb/s connection (2 x Ethernet RJ45 connection), but the interrogator limits connectivity to 1Gb/s. The collected data will be transmitted to INESC TEC’s storage infrastructure, which has a 2PB capacity. The Object Storage console uses MinIO, which is compatible with Amazon Web Storage (AWS) S3 protocol. Project users need an S3 client and access key to connect according with INESC TEC’s access guide (restricted use). The data will be stored for a period of three months, after which it will be overwritten to ensure sufficient space for the two Portuguese sites.

Figure 5 representative location of the submarine cable that links Sines (Portugal) to Fortaleza (Brazil).

3.2.1.2. Main challenges and Roadmap

Several challenges were encountered during the assessment process for equipment deployment. One of the major concerns is the risk of damaging the first repeater due to the high-power output of the OptoDAS (a Class 1M Laser product with a maximum output power of 21dBm). Additionally, EllaLink requires continuous access to perform operational control of the optical spectrum and power levels. Other relevant technical concerns have been addressed, including potential disturbances in the spectrum shape and the integrated power received at the CLS. Following a mutual agreement, the current CLS equipment configuration will be modified as Figure 6:

Figure 6 CLS interconnection a) before and b) after OptoDAS insertion. Note: CTB is the Cable Terminal Box and OSA is the Optical Spectrum Analyzer.

However, with the integration of a 50/50 fibre coupler, a 3dB loss in launch power will occur. Therefore, before connecting the OptoDAS, appropriate adjustments will be made at the Cable Terminal Box (CTB) monitoring point to achieve the designed launch power up to the first repeater. After connecting the OptoDAS to the fibre coupler, the operational wavelength window and output power will be configured to ensure the integrity of the transmission signal.

Regarding SOP data acquisition, the Polarimeter PolBox from CESNET has not yet been installed. The configuration of the submarine cable's data transmission system is currently being evaluated to determine the most suitable approach for implementing the polarimeter.

The roadmap for the Sines site is as follows:

- Finalize the network configuration to connect OptoDAS to the submarine cable.
- Complete the setup for remote access to the interrogator and data transmission.
- Integrate GPS equipment for time synchronization.
- Provide raw data to project partners via INESC TEC storage.
- Enable MiniSEED in OptoDAS and configure connectivity with IPMA. Note: MiniSEED is a simplified data format based on the Standard for the Exchange of Earthquake Data (SEED).
- Transmit data to IPMA's SEEDLINK system. Note: SEEDLINK is a network protocol used for transmitting seismological and environmental data in near real-time, primarily using the miniSEED format.

3.2.2 Madeira overall setup diagram and equipment

Figure 7 Madeira overall setup diagram and equipment.

The current equipment configuration in Madeira Island is depicted in Figure 7. The stakeholders of this site are the following:

- ARDITI, EllaLink, EMACOM, GEANT (Madeira Island) – Cable landing station (CLS) and GEOLAB submarine cable
- ARDITI – OptoDAS acquisition
- FCCN and GEANT – Connectivity
- INESC TEC – Storage (short-term)
- GFZ – Storage (long-term) and technical advisory
- FCUL-IDL – Remote data management
- ASN – OptoDAS technical support

3.2.2.1. Instrument deployment

The GeoLab is an infrastructure consisting of a spare fibre pair built into the Funchal branch of the EllaLink submarine telecommunications cable, which extends 57 km, south-east from the coast of Madeira, Portugal, into the Atlantic Ocean starting at the Praia Formosa CLS. Figure 8 shows a representative location of the submarine cable.

A C-band OptoDAS system (ASN), acquired by ARDITI, was connected to the G.652 optical fibre of the GEOLAB submarine cable using an FC/APC – LC/UPC singlemode fibre patchcord. FCCN provides a 1Gb/s connection (2 x Ethernet RJ45 connection). GPS for synchronization is available since June 2024, with an antenna installed on the roof of the CLS. The interrogation system has three point-to-point external connections: one to INESC TEC for data storage, one to IPMA for real-time data streaming, and one to FCUL-IDL for remote control and data management.

Initially, the collected data is streamed to a local short-term storage system connected to the OptoDAS unit. At this stage, data management is carried out by FCUL-IDL before the data is made available in a restricted-access area of INESC TEC’s storage infrastructure. Additionally, decimated miniSEED data will be transmitted to IPMA’s SEEDLINK server. A one-week archive of data is stored and distributed by the GFZ European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA) Node, including full-resolution raw files (HDF5 format) and decimated miniSEED data. FCUL-IDL also works on the algorithm to process and analyze subsets of data.

Figure 8 Representative location of the GEOLAB submarine cable, which extends 57 km from Madeira Island, Portugal.

3.2.2.2. Main challenges and Roadmap

The main challenges encountered all stem from the need to manage the equipment remotely, and the lack of internet connectivity for the server. Despite no internet connectivity, the system has three point-to-point connections to the outside: one to INESC TEC, for data storage; one to (The Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere) IPMA, for real-time data streaming; and one to Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon (FCUL), for remote control and direct upload and download of files.

After several rounds of technical support with ASN and FCCN, connectivity was finally established to FCUL, then to INESC TEC and, later, to IPMA. A bandwidth bottleneck existed between the CLS and the University of Madeira, but it has since been removed.

To provide streaming, an update of the server software and interrogator firmware were required. ASN devised an offline method to allow to perform such update without an internet connection. Nevertheless, the process was not straightforward, as some packages were missing and had to be uploaded separately.

The server is running OpenSuse Leap 15.4, which reached EOL (End of Life) in 2023, and ships with deprecated python versions. SEEDLink, and the Zero-MQ modules required newer versions. Currently, SEEDLink is configured to stream data, but no data is being captured from the interrogator. Past experience from GFZ has, so far, proved

insufficient, as the interrogator installed at GeoLab is now running a more up-to-date firmware version than other interrogators currently streaming to SEEDLink. ARDITI and GFZ are working together to solve this issue.

GeoLab provided the first DAS dataset uploaded to GFZ. Notable challenges were the definition of metadata, as there are still no agreed-upon standards.

The roadmap for the Madeira site is as follows:

- Finalize the configuration of the SEEDLink protocol to enable real-time streaming of decimated miniSEED data to IPMA. This data will later be made available to the community through the IPMA EIDA node once it becomes officially operational in the near future.
- Complete the setup for daily data upload to INESC TEC storage.
- Plan a server update to OpenSuse Leap 15.6.
- ARDITI will ensure the continuous recording of OptoDAS data in Madeira even after the conclusion of the SUBMERSE project.

The Table 4 summarizes the status of equipment deployment in Portugal as of 01.02.2025.

Site Name	Cable type and System	Sensing technology	Equipment deployment
Sines	Dark fibre, DWDM system	C-band OptoDAS	Performed in Q1.2025 Streaming data planned for Q2.2025
		Polbox SOP	Currently under technical assessment Planned for Q2.2025
Madeira Island	Dark fibre	C-band OptoDAS	In place since Q4.2023 Expected to be streaming data shortly.

Table 4 The status of equipment deployment in Portugal as of 01.02.2025.

3.3 Greece - Where are we at this stage compared with the ideal

The original plan for Greece involved installing an OptoDAS node in Rhodes on a dedicated fibre line. However, the high cost of acquiring this line was prohibitive, leading us to explore alternative options. One such alternative was utilizing the Preveza–Crotone link, operated by Islalink on behalf of Geant, while also conducting a feasibility study to assess the potential use of an L-band OptoDAS on the Rhodes-Kos link. Unfortunately, various challenges, including customs delays and setbacks in the delivery of the Preveza–Crotone link, significantly hindered deployment. Despite these obstacles, we secured a second OptoDAS from GFZ, and the feasibility study confirmed that deploying an L-band OptoDAS on the Rhodes-Kos link was viable without adverse effects. As a result, we are now in the process of deploying OptoDAS on both links."

3.3.1 Rhodes-Kos

The fibre optic cable starts at GRNET’s site (Greece National Infrastructures for Research and Technology) in Rhodes Island and links Rhodes to Kos. The cable is 160km long. It consists of 45km terrestrial cable running through the island of Rhodes and 115km submarine cable until the island of Kos. All 3 GRNET’s sites that are involved in this implementation are colocation sites provided by OTE, the largest technology company in Greece. The fibre pair belongs to GRNET with an IRU lease agreement of 20 years. Figure 9 shows a representative route of the total cable span.

Figure 9 Representative route of the total cable span

An L-band OptoDAS system, provided by ASN, was installed in GRNET’s rack in Rhodes and connected to the available fibre (dark fibre, G.652). An FC/APC – LC/UPC single mode fibre patchcord is required to connect the interrogator to the fibre under study. Currently this pair of fibre is being used for GRNET’s core optical network (equipment provided by Ribbon/ECI) so the implementation is done according to that. To insert the L-band OptoDAS signal into our production network we installed 3x C/L-filters. The Figure 10 shows our current connection diagram.

Figure 10 Current connection diagram

The signal starts from the OptoDAS system and enters the first C/L-filter at Rhodes site. Then it travels through the first part of the fibre cable (mainland) until our ILA site in Kamiros (Rhodes). There we have installed a second pair of C/L-filters bypassing the amplifiers of our core network. After that it enters the second part of the fibre cable (submarine) and travels until Kos island.

3.3.2 Preveza-Crotone

An OptoDAS was installed during the week 9, February 2025, by GFZ (Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences), IslaLink (Cable Operator), and NOA (The National Observatory of Athens). IslaLink prepared the site with a GPS antenna and receiver to provide precise time signal to the interrogator. For the management of the interrogator, and data transfer a 4G/5G router was installed on site, with a VPN connection to National Observatory of Athen. Mobile antennas for 4G/5G connectivity were installed outside as inside the signal was not strong enough.

- IslaLink cable, GFZ OptoDAS interrogator (80TB + 120TB Network-attached storage, NAS), hosting and national telecommunications GRNET, telecommunications from CLS and on-site hosting GÉANT.
- Decimated data flow to NOA initially via the 4G/5G; In the future, with the data connection provided by GÉANT (end of Q2), full resolution of data will be stored in the local buffer within GRNET. Until then data will only be stored in a local data buffer on the onsite NAS provided by GFZ as part of the OptoDAS system.

A data buffer of 99 days will be configured on the local NAS (120 TB) provided by GFZ. Additional capacity will be made available when GRNET provides additional local storage capacity. Once the terrestrial link to GRNET is established, data will be daily synchronised to a local data storage at GRNET, and made available to authorized users (alongside with precise metadata of the cable). GRNET is expected to provide up to 1PB of buffer data storage capacity.

Configuration parameters as defined in the data policy document "Data Management Policy Preveza-IslaLink site (DAS) F. Tilmann, C. Evangelidis, A. Strollo,V1.1 3-1-2025" for full resolution data stored as 250 HZ instead

of 200 as only integer decimation factors accepted by OptoDAS. Note also the gauge length has been changed to 20, instead of the originally planned 10 because OptoDAS setup recommended to have spatial sampling smaller than gauge l.):

- Gauge length 20m spatial sampling 10, sampling frequency (pulse) 500 Hz
- Decimation factor 2 => 250 Hz stored locally and on NAS (Local 84TB, NAS 126TB storage size)
- Decimation factor 5 => 100 Hz ZeroMQ to seedlink => NOA =>GFZ (spatial decimation 1/100)
- Storage configured in buffer mode for 99 days on both local and external DAS

Figure 11 320km un-repeated sea cable between Crotona and Preveza owned by IslaLink.

3.3.3 Buffer

GRNET decided to handle data transfer, storage, and preprocessing within its data centre in Knossos, Crete. To facilitate this, two virtual machines (VMs) were deployed as gateways to the storage appliance (NetApp), which acts as a buffer for the output from the OptoDAS systems deployed on the Kos-Rhodes and Preveza-Crotona links. For security, both systems will communicate with the storage VMs via a secure TLS channel. Since the buffer resides in the Knossos data centre, ample computing capacity is available to process and clean the data before it is sent for scientific analysis and archiving.

3.3.4 Next Steps

The next Steps for both use cases is to establish a secure connection from the OptoDAS system to the Buffer Service and to start defining the process to clean up the data to be distributed for further analysis.

4 Conclusions

The installation of sensing devices discussed in this document is like installation of any other network equipment in a server or communication room but with some additional concern regarding acoustic noise and vibrational acceleration noise which should be at a minimum level as possible.

Choose of optical fibre is important but not essential. The recommendation is using silica core fibre with low loss as it is used for general telecommunication purposes.

The main challenge is to identify security issues regarding the data management and identify the national shareholder/s who has authority and expertise to analyse and interpret the data from DAS specific and also generally from all type of sensing devices.

Coordination between the shareholders and agree upon a clear interface and responsibilities between them is key issue to success.

References

[Reference]

[link](#)

Glossary

ASN	Alcatel Submarine Networks
AWS	Amazon Web Storage
BIPM	Bureau International des Poids et Mesures
C-band	Conventional band, 1530-1565 nm wavelength range in fibre-optic communications
CGF	Center for Geophysical Forecasting
CLS	Cable landing station
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensor
dBm	Decibels relative to 1 milliwatt
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSP	Digital Signal Processors
DWDM	Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing
EIDA	European Integrated Data Archive
EllaLink	A company and an optical submarine cable system linking Europe and South America
ELSTAB	Electronically Stabilised time and frequency over fibre
ePIC	ePIC Persistent Identifier Consortium
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FCUL	Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon
Galileo	A European owned and run GNSS.
GÉANT	Pan-European Research and Education Network
GFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRNET	Greece National Infrastructures for Research and Technology
HTTP API	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Application Programming Interface
ILA	In Line Amplifier
IPMA	The Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere
L-band	Long band, 1565-1625 nm wavelength range in fibre-optic communications
NREN	National Research and Education Network
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
NOA	The National Observatory of Athens
OAuth 2.0	Open Authorization standard

OIDC	OpenID Connect
OTDR	Optical Time Domain Reflectometry
Post-FEC BER	Post Forward-error-correction Bit Error Rate
Pre-FEC BER	Pre Forward-error-correction Bit Error Rate
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
Q-factor	Quality factor
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SDU	Signal Distribution Units
Sirtfi	Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity
SoP	State of Polarisation
SUBMERSE	Submarine Cables for Research and Exploration
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TS	Time Server
UAH	University of Alcalá
URL	Unique Resource Location
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
UTC-USNO	United States Naval Observatory time standard
VM	Virtual Machine (VM)
WRS	White Rabbit Switch